

HJRS Link: [Journal of Academic Research for Humanities \(HEC-Recognized for 2022-2023\)](#)

Edition Link: [Journal of Academic Research for Humanities, 3\(2\) April-June 2023](#)

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Link of the Paper: <https://jar.bwo.org.pk/index.php/jarh/article/view/248>

EFFECTS OF WORKING FROM HOME ON EMPLOYEE PRODUCTIVITY: A STUDY ON THE EDUCATION SECTOR OF PAKISTAN

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Paper Information

Citation of the paper:

(APA) Abbasi. Aqib Hussain and Waseem. Syeda Nazneen, (2023). Effects of Working from Home on Employee Productivity: A Study on the Education Sector of Pakistan. Journal of Academic Research for Humanities, 3(2), 110–117.

Subject Areas:

- 1 Economic
- 2 Humanities

Timeline of the Paper:

Received on: 07-04-2023
Reviews Completed on: 08-05-2023
Accepted on: 10-05-2023
Online on: 11-05-2023

License:

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Recognized:

Published by:

Abstract

Pakistan faces numerous challenges in providing quality education to all its citizens, particularly online education. In this study, we examined the relationships between elements connected to working from home such as work-life balance, Employees Mental health, Technological advancement, Employee Performance, and Jobs satisfaction. The information was collected throughout Karachi. Clifton, Gulshan- Hyderi- Nazimabad, and I.I Chundrigar Road, Tariq Road, and Zamzama]. Despite the population's high degree of intermixture, the small samples (600 hundred people were chosen, and 100 people from each area were interviewed with equal gender i.e. both male and female). The Analysis of data is based on the triangular method to see the impact on productivity. In the triangulation approach, we have used a combination of qualitative and quantitative data sources and methods, such as surveys, interviews, observations, and document analysis. The path analysis was conducted using hypotheses testing and discriminant validity using Fornell and Larcker criterion (FLC). The results of the PLS algorithm technique suggest that Working from home has a positive impact on employee performance. Work-life balance has moderating effects while working from home. Working from home increases the efficiency of employees in the organization. The mental health of employees has a positive effect on working from home. Job satisfaction is achieved while working from home. Technological development has accentuated work from home. Future research could focus on the long-term effects of remote work and designing measures to cope with those issues.

Keywords: Remote work, telework practices, telework management. Work from Home, Online Work

Introduction

To explore the impact of WFH on employee productivity in the education sector of Pakistan and identify strategies to enhance Productivity in the new WFH paradigm. Education is pivotal for the development of the country. The development and progress of the state do not only depend upon the quality of education but also on the literacy rate of the country at large. Education is not only the right of people but also social, economic, cultural, and religious rights also. Many CEOs and Managers believe Working from home is considered not good but fortunately, companies are converting their policies to work from home. Employers have no confidence in their employees because the workers would be distracted at home. Working from home is a recent phenomenon. It was an exceptional decade ago. Teleconferencing and telework are the pioneering instruments for working from home. A decade ago, it was out of the question and employers were shivering about the idea of people working from home. The major objection was that it would affect productivity. How is the effective management of employees because the workers are not under evaluation in the process? The encouraging statistics compel both employees and employers to formulate and adopt the program of work-from-home. In recent Eras, Many Organizations believe that Remote employees are more effective than office bound-employees. People were unaware of the idea of working from home. The business deal was made due to face to discourse. Email, Fax, laser, and Scanners were utilized. But the work-from-home concept strategy was enhanced by technology.

Today, full-time, work-from-home has emerged regular job strategy. Automation and improved technology have lessened the distance between and among people. Working from home is gaining ground in education sectors and adopting various ways to communicate and share information with

students. There are relatively lower conditions of education in Pakistan as compared to developed countries in terms of Online Education. The recent past education system crumbled and class cleavages increased manifolds. In Pakistan. Generally, E-learning is performed with Zoom, Google Edmond, Hangout, Facebook, WhatsApp, and Immo, etc. The Higher Education Commission of Pakistan (HEC) encouraged and guided university administration in conducting online classes. Online Education is an advanced technology through which universities reached /conveyed education beyond borders. The new rules and regulations may be adopted while preventing the negative impact on the health, productivity, and security of workers. Employees should be encouraged according to market-based incentives. New regulations must be put in place to ensure that these practices did not negatively affect the comfort, health, and safety of remote workers, and companies are encouraged to move in this positive direction.

Research Objectives

1. To find out the present prospects of working from home in Pakistan.
2. To find out the prospect of working from home in Pakistan.
3. To find out the barriers to working from home in the education sector of Pakistan.

Research Questions

- 1-What are the benefits of working from home for an organization?
- 2-How working from home affects the balance of life?
- 3- Is there any effect of working from home on employee performance?
- 4- To what extent does working from home affect mental health?
- 5- Are there any advantages of working from home for job satisfaction?
- 6-Does technological advancement accentuate working from home?

Hypotheses:

- H1₀- Working from home is beneficial for the organization.

- H1₁- Working from home is not beneficial for an organization.
- H2₀- Working from home affects the balance of life.
- H2₁- Working from home does not affect the balance of life.
- H3₀- Working from home on employees' performance has a direct effect.
- H3₁- Working from home on employees' performance has no direct effect.
- H3₀- Working from home cause complications in the mental health of an employee
- H3₁- Working from home does not cause complications in the mental health of employees.
- H4₀- Work from home has advantages for job satisfaction.
- H4₁- Working from home has not advantageous for job satisfaction.
- H5₀- Technological advancement has accentuated work from home.
- H5₁- Technological advancement has not accentuated work from home.

Theoretical Framework

Dependent variable :

Employee Performance.

Moderator:

Technological advancement.

Mediating Variables:

Work-life balance
Job Satisfaction
Mental Health

Independent Variable

Work from Home

Methodology:

The triangular methodology is adopted. In the triangulation approach, we have used a combination of qualitative and quantitative data sources and methods, such as surveys, interviews, observations, and document analysis. In this technique, the methods i.e. **Quantitative and Qualitative** are used according to the needs of the developing hypothesis. Both research methods are important. A questionnaire was used to personally collect primary data. The information was collected throughout Karachi. Clifton, Gulshan- Hyderi- Nazimabad, and I.I Chundrigar Road, Tariq Road, and Zamzama]. Despite the population's high degree of intermixture, the small samples (600 hundred people were chosen, and 100 people from each area were interviewed with equal gender (i.e. both and females) and were carefully chosen from Karachi's upscale education districts because the population there has a foundation of knowledge and skills. PLS (Partial least squares), was used to analyze 6 different variables the path analysis was conducted using hypotheses testing and discriminant validity using **Fornell and Larcker criterion** (FLC). In addition to other questions pertinent to the research analysis, the analysis covered all questions and hypotheses.

- The gender of the person was identified in the survey.
- The study included a person's age.
- The educational qualification of the interview was also included in the study.
- The question of professional qualifications was also raised.
- Service time is interpreted in the form.
- Nature of knowledge explained.
- Questions about communication between colleagues.
- A question is asked about information gathering.
- We ask about the time value of money.

For each variable/research question/hypothesis, a comprehensive

analysis of data collected from primary sources was analyzed.

Literature Review

According to research by Bloom et al. (2015), remote employees were 13% more productive than their office-based colleagues. This is because remote workers were better equipped to manage their time and faced fewer distractions. In a subsequent study, Gajendran and Harrison (2007) discovered that remote workers were more effective and content with their jobs than office-based employees.

The degree of team member participation and communication can also have an impact on the association between productivity and working from home. According to a study by Gajendran and Harrison (2007), telecommuters who communicated with their coworkers frequently were more productive than those who communicated with them infrequently.

Numerous research have looked into the connection between productivity and working remotely. Connelly et al. (2016) found no significant influence on productivity, while remote workers reported higher levels of job satisfaction and engagement. The researcher's hypotheses stated that this may be because remote workers frequently exhibit greater autonomy and control over their work schedules, which results in higher job satisfaction but not necessarily higher productivity.

Similarly, a study by Sardeshmukh et al. (2012) discovered that while telecommuting did boost job satisfaction and lower turnover intentions, it had no appreciable impact on job performance. According to the authors, telecommuting may result in a better work-life balance and reduced stress from commuting, which can increase overall job satisfaction and retention. On the other side, a meta-analysis by Gajendran and Harrison (2007) discovered that telecommuting improved job performance, particularly for difficult or mentally taxing activities. The authors contend

that telecommuting can boost productivity for some jobs by reducing interruptions and distractions. Nijp et al.'s (2021) more recent research discovered that telecommuting during the COVID-19 pandemic increased productivity, particularly for individuals with high degrees of task dependency and social support. The authors contend that reduced travel time and more workplace autonomy are two benefits of remote work that can boost total output.

Collaboration and communication are significant aspects that can impact the relationship between remote work and productivity in addition to the nature of the job. According to a study by Gajendran and Harrison (2007), telecommuters who communicated with their coworkers frequently were more productive than those who communicated with them infrequently. Similarly to this, Nijp et al.'s (2021) study discovered that social support from coworkers and managers can mitigate the detrimental impacts of remote work on workload and burnout. In conclusion, the research so far indicates that, depending on the requirements of the position and the degree of interaction and cooperation with coworkers, remote work may have both favorable and unfavorable effects on employee productivity. Employers should be aware of potential productivity difficulties and put in place techniques to facilitate communication and collaboration among remote workers even though remote work might increase job satisfaction and work-life balance. To fully comprehend the complicated relationship between remote work and productivity, work-life balance, job happiness, and employees' mental health, more research is required.

Quantitative Research Method:

There were about 600 people were involved in this research methodology out of which 50 percent were male and 300 were female respectively. The study was confined to Karachi only. A questionnaire was used to personally collect primary data. The

	W.F.H	W.L.B	J.S	M.H	E.P	T.A	W.L.B*J.S	M.H*E.P
Work from Home - W.F.H								
Work-life Balance - W.L.B	0.818							
JOB Satisfaction- J.S	0.298	0.328						
Mental Health M.H	0.674	0.639	0.574					
Employee Performance - E.P	0.838	0.765	0.444	0.837				
Technological Advancement- T.A	0.591	0.647	0.634	0.764	0.762			
Work-life balance x Job satisfaction- W.L.B x J.S	0.417	0.467	0.346	0.733	0.628	0.466		
Mental health x Employee performance - M.H*E.P	0.359	0.369	0.287	0.701	0.507	0.386	0.801	

information was collected throughout Karachi. Clifton, Gulshan- Hyderi- Nazimabad, and. I.I Chundrigar Road, Tariq Road, and Zamzama]. Despite the population's high degree of intermixture, the small samples and were carefully chosen from Karachi's upscale education districts because the population there has a foundation of knowledge and skills. PLS (Partial least squares), was used to analyze 6 different variables.

Construct Validity and Reliability Matrix:

Table 1

Cronbach's alpha	Composit reliability (rho_a)	Composit reliability (rho_c)	Average variance extracte d (AVE)
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Work from Home	0.944	0.946	0.956	0.779
Work-Life Balance	0.948	0.951	0.965	0.868
Job satisfaction	0.902	0.928	0.923	0.599
Mental health	0.905	0.921	0.928	0.724
Employee performance	0.931	0.932	0.941	0.671
Technological Advancement	0.917	0.926	0.932	0.578

The table provides measures of construct validity for six different constructs in the research, including Work from Home, Work life balance job satisfaction mental health, Employee performance, and Technological. The measures include Cronbach's alpha, Composite reliability advancement (rho_a), Composite reliability (rho_c), and Average Variance Extracted (AVE).

Overall, the table provides evidence of strong construct validity for the five constructs in the Research indicating that they are reliable and measure what they are intended to measure. It is important to note that these measures were obtained from a particular sample and may not generalize to other populations.

Discriminant Validity and Reliability

This discriminant validity HTMT matrix shows the strength of the correlations between the variables in the study. All values in the matrix represent the square root of the average variance extracted (AVE) of each variable, divided by the heterograft-monotrait (HTMT) ratio of the correlations between the variable and all other variables in the study. A value below 0.85 indicates that the variable has good discriminant validity, meaning that it is measuring a unique construct that is not highly correlated with other constructs in the study. Looking at the matrix, all values are below the threshold of 0.85, indicating good discriminant validity for all variables. Work-life Balance has the highest correlation with job satisfaction (0.839), followed by mental health (0.674), technological advancement (0.591), and job satisfaction (0.299). Job satisfaction has a strong positive correlation with work-life

balance (0.818), suggesting that they are opposite constructs that affect each.

The values suggest that the variables are not highly correlated and that they have good discriminant validity for use in statistical analyses.

FORNELL-LARCKER MATRIX

The Fornell-Larcker matrix is a tool used in structural equation modeling to assess the discriminant validity of construct measures. The matrix displays the square root of the average variance extracted (AVE) for each construct on the diagonal, and the correlations between the constructs on the off-diagonal.

In the matrix, the variables are: Work from Home, Work-Life Balance, Job Satisfaction, Mental Health, Employee Performance, Technological Advancement

The matrix provides the following information:

Mental health has a high correlation with Employee performance (0.788), indicating that these constructs share a significant amount of variance. It also has a moderate positive correlation with Technological advancement (0.562) and a weak positive correlation with Job satisfaction (0.300).

Job satisfaction has a moderate positive correlation with work-life balance (0.300) and Technological advancement (0.579), and a weak positive correlation with Work-life balance (0.531) and employee performance (0.415).

Work-life balance has a strong positive correlation with mental health (0.820) and a moderate positive correlation with employee performance (0.636), and technological advancement (0.702). Technological advancement has a moderate positive correlation with all other constructs:

Employee performance (0.561),

Overall, the matrix indicates that the constructs have adequate discriminant validity, as the diagonal values (AVE) are higher than the correlations between constructions.

Analysis

In detail, the study shows how students in Pakistan perceive and use online learning opportunities. By examining general key elements like the function of university and teacher support during online learning, the positive and negative influencing factors connected to online environments, the impact of home learning and resource accessibility, and more, a gap in the literature is also addressed. In the growth of online learning in a developing nation where opportunities, resources, and infrastructure are constrained.

The study was carried out at a time when online/distance learning was being used in almost all educational institutions across the nation. The lack of consistent coordination between various institutions and ministries was one of the most important factors. Nearly half of Pakistan's population lives in rural areas with observable technical issues. All students must be able to continue their education online, so the respective educational institutions must create a functional infrastructure. Since the digital libraries in Punjab province are outfitted with the newest technology and infrastructure, they can be used for online classes. But to accomplish this, the Higher Education Commission (HEC), Higher Education Institutions (HEI), Pakistan Telecommunication Authority (PTA), and the Ministry of Information Technology and Telecommunication (MOITT) must work effectively together. The planning, carrying out, and evaluation of online lessons should be a major focus for colleges and universities when training their faculty.

Results & Findings.

- 1- Working at home for the organization is beneficial for organizational development.
- 2- Working at home affects the balance of life.
- 3- Working at home increases the efficiency of employees in the organization.
- 4- Working from home to relax the mental health of employees
- 5- Working from home is a source of job satisfaction.

6-Technological development has accentuated work from home

Research Recommendations & Suggestions.

Follow these steps to work from home.

- 1-Remote workers may find it harder to feel like part of a team
- 2-Staying motivated and focused can be difficult
- 3-Risk of burnout
- 4-Part of their employment contracts.
- 5-Regular meetings and discussions
- 6-Make clear expectations
- 7-Find and hire the right people.
- 8-Documentation of regular processes
- 9 - Management style is the key.

Conclusion:

After analyzing and testing hypotheses it is clear that working from home has a direct relation with Employees performance, working from home has enabled flexible working hours, which boosts employees' productivity, and has a positive impact on the mental health of employees, Technological advancement has played a crucial role in facilitating and has enabled the working from home. Today, people must have certain skills to survive and succeed in this competitive world. These skills can be called education. Education demonstrates a significant role in the prosperity and enhancing the development of the country. The success of any country relies on literacy and the quality of meritorious education in that country. It is therefore a priority for countries. In Pakistan, education policy reflects ideology. It is composed of political and alternatives, traditions, values, norms, culture, socio-economic needs, new development trends, and future concepts and even their consequences in the future. For some time, information technology has opened different ways of organizing work that competes with old management methods. Advanced structures of organizations have initiated to offer a variety of options to cater to the increasing demand for flexibility in work. With appropriate tools supporting remote work,

this new way of working has expanded rapidly in recent decades. As a result, virtual team members today increasingly work remotely from home or a satellite office to reduce commuting. Telecommuting, working from home, or telecommuting, whatever you call it, internships are here to stay. The current environment not only makes almost any organization a potential case study but also offers a chance to examine global telecommunications trends, potentially providing all the information required to adapt telecommunications initiatives to different countries/cultures. Companies are always looking for new ways to maximize the benefits of remote work and minimize its drawbacks, so policymakers must take more active and direct action to address telework and its effects. To ensure that these actions do not negatively impact organizations, new regulations should be put in place.

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